

Set of 40 studies of different patients.

ID: 9e0c5bb0-a93c-484c-a417-888cc93b5939

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 40

Subjects count: 40

Age range: Between 41 years and 81 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, THORAX / ABDOMEN, HEAD, LUNG, TAP, CRANE, WHOLEBODY, Unknown

Modality: CT, DX